

ANALYSIS OF GENETIC DIVERSITY IN SOME PURPLE CARROT GENOTYPES

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ABSTRACT. The carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) is a significant vegetable species that is taxonomically classified within the *Apiaceae* family. The edible parts of the carrot include its roots and hypocotyl stems, and it exhibits a substantial degree of genetic diversity. Purple carrots are important for health due to their high anthocyanin content and are preferred in the food industry as a natural food colorant. The present study was conducted with the objective of ascertaining the genetic diversity of purple carrot genotypes. Determining genetic diversity is of great importance to achieve successful results in breeding studies. In this context, genetic characterization was performed using 31 purple carrot genotypes in the S4 stage. Following DNA isolation, target regions were amplified by PCR analysis, and polymorphic alleles were determined by electrophoresis. The resulting data were then analyzed using the DarWin package program to create a dendrogram, which was employed to determine the genetic relationships between the genotypes. A total of 62 alleles were detected within the scope of the study, 87% of which were defined as polymorphic. The highest observed levels of polymorphism were identified in the GSSR153 and GSSR152 markers, while genetic similarity rates ranged from 0.07 to 0.57. The analysis results indicated that the genotypes examined were grouped into three main groups and revealed that some genotypes exhibited divergent genetic structures by demonstrating more distant branching patterns compared to others. The Mantel test, utilised within the present study for the purpose of evaluating the reliability of genetic association analyses, returned a value $r=0.88$, thereby substantiating the validity of the employed methodology. The data obtained reveal that the genetic diversity is high among purple carrot genotypes, and that this variation includes valuable genotypes that could be used in breeding programs. In particular, the identification of genetically distinct genotypes offers a significant advantage in enhancing the heterosis effect in hybrid breeding programs. The genetic structures detected in the study provide important data for breeding programs, such as the protection of purple carrot genetic resources and the development of new varieties.

Keywords: *Dendrogram, purple carrot, genetic diversity, InDel, molecular markers, SSR*

INTRODUCTION

Carrot (*Daucus carota*) is a vegetable species that completes its developmental process in two years, is known for its nutritional value, colour and flavour diversity, and is consumed with its roots and hypocotyl stem belonging to the *Apiaceae* family [1]. The primary genetic centre of carrots is thought to be Afghanistan, while the secondary genetic centre is suggested to be Turkey [2, 3]. In addition to their anthocyanin content, purple carrots are increasingly used as a natural food colour in the food industry due to their vibrant colour [4, 5].

To successfully complete breeding studies, it is imperative to have a diverse gene pool and to be familiar with the morphological and genetic characteristics of the materials in this pool [6, 7]. By using these materials with a known genetic background, it is possible to develop varieties with superior characteristics in terms of yield and quality parameters, tolerant to abiotic stress factors, and resistant to diseases and pests [8]. As with all plants, the genetic diversity of purple carrots is of significance for the purposes of breeding studies [9]. Significant genetic and phenotypic diversity is exhibited by purple carrots, especially regarding anthocyanin content, which contributes to their antioxidant capacity, thus being beneficial to

human health [10]. The nutritional content of purple carrots can be increased by using genotypes containing these compounds [10].

Simple sequence repeats (SSR) markers have been shown to offer distinct advantages in the domain of genetic diversity analysis, attributable to their unique characteristics and applications. In the context of breeding processes across many plant species, these elements are favoured due to their numerous advantages. These include elevated levels of polymorphism, the capacity to discern a substantial number of alleles, detecting heterozygous alleles due to their co-dominant characteristics, and their pervasive distribution throughout the genome [11-14]. In addition, single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) and insertion-deletion (InDel) markers, which are stated as third-generation DNA markers, are widely used in plant genetic research due to their co-dominant properties and wide distribution over the whole genome in plants [15,16]. Techniques such as SNP and SSR markers are utilised to assess genetic diversity and population structure, thereby providing information on different samples' genetic relationships and potential [17]. The use of molecular markers is becoming increasingly prevalent in carrot studies, with various markers resulting in more precise results in direct breeding studies. AFLP, ISSR, and SSR markers are frequently utilised in genetic diversity studies on carrots [18-21].

The present study used molecular markers to ascertain the genetic diversity of 31 carrot genotypes in the S4 stage. The data obtained from the study were evaluated to determine the potential of the current gene pool for future breeding programmes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

Within the scope of the study, seeds of 31 purple carrot genotypes obtained from commercial and local sources and self-pollinated to the S4 stage were used. After the seeds germinated, leaf samples were taken and stored at -20 °C, and DNA studies and PCR analyses were performed on these materials.

DNA isolation and PCR analysis

The genetic diversity of the genotypes was determined by DNA isolation from leaves stored in a cold environment at -20°C. The process of DNA isolation was conducted in accordance with the CTAB protocol as outlined by Doyle and Doyle [22]. SSR and InDEL markers listed in Table 1 were provided for genetic diversity analysis, and PCR studies were completed using these primers.

Genetic Diversity Analysis

PCR procedures were performed by considering the binding temperatures determined in accordance with the primers in Table 1. Upon completion of PCR procedures, images were obtained by gel electrophoresis, and alleles in these images were scored according to the presence-absence principle. Diversity analyses were performed using the data obtained because of running PCR products by gel electrophoresis and scoring polymorphic alleles. The data were evaluated and analysed in DarWin package programme and dendrograms and genetic maps were created. Polymorphism information content of DNA markers was calculated using the formula specified by Weir [26].

Table 1. Primers and reference information used in the study

Markers	References
BSSR013	Cavagnaro et al. [23]
BSSR039	Cavagnaro et al. [23]
BSSR043	Cavagnaro et al. [23]
ESSR011	Cavagnaro et al. [23]
OPK9	Cavagnaro et al. [23]
y2	Cavagnaro et al. [23]
ESSR058	Iorizzo et al. [24]
GSSR122	Iorizzo et al. [24]
GSSR149	Iorizzo et al. [24]
GSSR152	Iorizzo et al. [24]
GSSR153	Iorizzo et al. [24]
GSSR154	Iorizzo et al. [24]
yY-W Indel	Iorizzo et al. [1]
PSY2	Uncu ve Uncu [13]
SSR2-3G	Uncu ve Uncu [13]
Q1/850	Rong et al. [25]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the study context, molecular diversity analyses were conducted utilising the available primers. The outcomes of the molecular characterisation studies are presented in Figure 1. The phenograms derived from the study revealed the presence of 62 alleles, of which 54 were found to be polymorphic and eight were monomorphic. In the initial stage, the scoring of these alleles was based on their base lengths. To ensure compatibility with the package programme for data processing, the scoring was designated as 1 for the presence of each allele and 0 for its absence. The program designated samples that did not fit this pattern as 'missing data' (9). Utilising the revised polymorphic alleles, a dendrogram was constructed employing the Dice similarity coefficient in the DarWin 6 package programme (Fig. 1).

In the present study, 16 markers were utilised for genetic diversity analysis, with 14 of these markers producing polymorphic bands. However, it was observed that markers BSSR013 and BSSR039 could not produce polymorphic alleles. The primer pairs employed were subjected to a polymorphism information content (PIC) calculation, as Botstein et al. [27] outlined, and the resulting data are presented in Table 2. The PIC values of the markers ranged between 0.49 and 0.04, with a mean PIC value of 0.2611. The marker GSSR149 exhibited the highest PIC value of 0.4898, while the marker y2 demonstrated the lowest PIC value of 0.037. The total number of polymorphic alleles produced was 54, with the highest number obtained from markers GSSR153 and GSSR152.

A thorough examination of the dendrogram in Figure 1, derived from the DarWin 6 package programme utilising the revised polymorphic alleles, reveals classification of carrot genotypes into three primary groups. These groups were further subdivided into smaller subgroups. Here, the branches show the closeness and distance between the genotypes. In other words, genotypes with long branching structures are less similar, while those with similar genetic characteristics show a shorter branching structure.

Table 2. PIC values of primers used in genetic diversity analysis

Marker	PIC value
GSSR149	0,4898
BSSR043	0,4495
ESSR058	0,4112
GSSR153	0,3148
GSSR152	0,305
yY-W Indel	0,2968
GSSR122	0,2281
Q1/850	0,2101
OPK9	0,2096
GSSR154	0,2066
ESSR011	0,1859
SSR2-3G	0,1568
PSY2	0,155
y2	0,037

Fig. 1. Dendrogram obtained as a result of molecular characterisation study

According to this information, when the dendrogram was analysed, genotypes 3-7-30-4 and 68-9-3-6 formed the most different group by being connected to the genotypes from the outside. When the extreme values obtained from the programme are examined with the dendrogram, the closeness of the genotypes can be understood more clearly. The average distance of the genotypes was found to be 0.33. This value and the dendrogram image show that there are different individuals in the gene pool and there is genetic diversity.

The most distant genotypes from each other were 69-4-11-2 and 5-15-1-2, with 0.57. In addition, genotypes 69-4-11-2 / 13-6-1-2 and OT 22-1-1 / 15-2-2-3 had a distance of 0.56 and 0.55, respectively, and were found to be quite different from each other. As a result of the genetic diversity analysis, it can be stated that the closest genotypes are 69-4-11-2 and 69-4-11-1, with 0.07, and genotypes 51-14-22-14 and 7-5-8-1. When the other genotypes were analysed, genotypes OT-22-2-1, 7-5-8-1, 5-13-1-1, and 13-6-1-3 were the genetically closest genotypes (Figure 1).

After creating the dendrograms, the Mantel test was applied with the same package programme. The Mantel test aims to determine the extent to which the data in the scoring data match the drawn dendrogram. As the scoring data's accuracy will demonstrate the drawn dendrogram's reliability in revealing the genetic relationship, this test was necessary. While the acceptable range of the r value obtained from the Mantel test varies between 0.85 and 1, the proximity of this value to 1 indicates the reliability of the study. The Mantel test undertaken within the scope of the study yielded an r value of 0.88, thereby demonstrating the reliability of the study's data.

Dendrogram analyses were utilised as a significant instrument to determine the genetic distances between genotypes. The obtained dendrogram demonstrated that three primary groups were formed, with the genetically most distant genotypes exhibiting a Dice similarity coefficient of 0.57. Conversely, the closest genotypes were observed to be adjacent, with 0.07. In a related study, İpek et al. [18] analysed the diversity of purple carrot genotypes cultivated in the Konya Ereğli district, reporting genetic similarities ranging from 0.26 to 0.70. Their analysis, employing a dendrogram, identified three distinct clusters within the population. In a different study, an investigation was conducted into the diversity of purple carrots cultivated in the Central Anatolia Region. This study aimed to ascertain the genetic diversity of purple carrot genotypes in Central Anatolia by employing AFLP and ISSR methods. The molecular data of 23 genotypes obtained from Hatay and Konya were subjected to UPGMA analysis, which revealed that the genotypes fell within the similarity range of 0.54-0.94. Examination of the dendrogram showed that the population was divided into two main branches, with the population consisting of four subpopulations [28]. Codominant microsatellite (SSR) markers were used in a study conducted to screen the internal genetic diversity of 18 cultivated carrot populations of different origins, codominant microsatellite (SSR) markers were used. 27 genomic and EST-derived SSR markers were used to detect 253 alleles, with an average of 9.4 alleles per marker. Genomic SSR markers showed more polymorphism than EST-derived SSR markers. In addition, 16 of the 18 populations belonged to the Western or Asian carrot gene pool. Most of the genetic diversity of the population in the study was due to allelic variation among individuals (62%), while the variation among populations was calculated as 38% [29]. These findings indicate a wide genetic variation among purple carrot genotypes and that specific genotypes can be considered parents in breeding programmes.

CONCLUSION

This study utilized SSR and InDel markers to ascertain the genetic diversity of purple carrot genotypes. The genetic profile of 31 purple carrot genotypes at the S4 level was determined. According to the results obtained, 62 alleles were detected, 87% of which were determined as

polymorphic. Genetic similarity analyses showed that the genotypes were divided into three main groups, with some genotypes having a more distant genetic structure than others. The findings of this study indicate that the genetic diversity among the purple carrot genotypes is high. In conclusion, this study has demonstrated that genetic diversity in purple carrot genotypes can be successfully measured. The data obtained will inform breeding programmes and the management of genetic resources. Future studies, supported by broader genetic analyses, will contribute to obtaining more in-depth genetic information for purple carrot breeding.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Iorizzo, M., Ellison, S., Senalik, D., Zeng, P., Satapoomin, P., Huang, J. Bowman, M., Iovene, M., Sanseverino, W., Cavagnaro, P., Yildiz, M., Macko-Podgorni, A., Moranska, E., Grzebelus, E., Ashrafi, H., Zheng, Z., Cheng, S., Spooner, D., Deynze, A., Simon, P. (2016): A high-quality carrot genome assembly provides new insights into carotenoid accumulation and asterid genome evolution. *Nature genetics*, 48(6): 657-666.
- [2] Ellison, S. (2019): Carrot domestication, *The carrot genome*, 77-91.
- [3] Singh, B. K., Koley, T. K., Maurya, A., Singh, P. M., Singh, B. (2018): Phytochemical and antioxidative potential of orange, red, yellow, rainbow and black coloured tropical carrots (*Daucus carota* subsp. *sativus* Schubl. & Martens). *Physiology and Molecular Biology of Plants*, 24: 899-907.
- [4] Perez, M. B., Hamparsomian, M. J. D. P., Gonzalez, R. E., Denoya, G. I., Dominguez, D. L., Barboza, K., Cavagnaro, P. F. (2022): Physicochemical properties, degradation kinetics, and antioxidant capacity of aqueous anthocyanin-based extracts from purple carrots compared to synthetic and natural food colorants. *Food chemistry*, 387: 132893.
- [5] Soares, G. R., Moura, C. F. G. d., Silva, M. J. D., Vilegas, W., Santamarina, A. B., Pisani, L. P., Ribeiro, D. A. (2018): Protective effects of purple carrot extract (*Daucus carota*) against rat tongue carcinogenesis induced by 4-nitroquinoline 1-oxide. *Medical Oncology*, 35(4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12032-018-1114-7>
- [6] Mastrangelo, A. M., Hartings, H., Lanzanova, C., Balconi, C., Locatelli, S., Cassol, H., Pecchioni, N. (2024): Genetic Diversity within a Collection of Italian Maize Inbred Lines: A Resource for Maize Genomics and Breeding. *Plants*, 13(3): 336.
- [7] Govindaraj, M., Vetriventhan, M., Srinivasan, M. (2015): Importance of genetic diversity assessment in crop plants and its recent advances: an overview of its analytical perspectives. *Genetics research international*, 2015(1): 431487.
- [8] Brbaklić, L., Trkulja, D., Mikić, S., Mirosavljević, M., Momčilović, V., Dudić, B., Procházková, L., Aćin, V. (2021): Genetic Diversity and Population Structure of Serbian Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) Collection during a 40-Year Long Breeding Period. *Agronomy*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/AGRONOMY11010118>.
- [9] Bhandari, S., Rhee, J., Choi, C., Jo, J., Shin, Y., Song, J., Kim, S., Lee, J. (2022): Morphological and Biochemical Variation in Carrot Genetic Resources Grown under Open Field Conditions: The Selection of Functional Genotypes for a Breeding Program. *Agronomy*.
- [10] Pérez, M. B., Carvajal, S., Beretta, V., Bannoud, F., Fangio, M. F., Berli, F., Cavagnaro, P. F. (2023): Characterization of purple carrot germplasm for antioxidant capacity and root concentration of anthocyanins, phenolics, and carotenoids. *Plants*, 12(9): 1796.
- [11] Bhardwaj, V., Kumar, A., Sharma, S., Singh, B., Poonam, Sood, S., Kumar, D. (2023): Analysis of genetic diversity, population structure and association mapping for late blight resistance in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) accessions using SSR markers. *Agronomy*, 13(2): 294.

- [12] Özkan, G., Haliloğlu, K., Türkoğlu, A., Öztürk, H., Elkoca, E., Poczai, P. (2022): Determining Genetic Diversity and Population Structure of Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Landraces from Türkiye Using SSR Markers. *Genes*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes13081410>.
- [13] Uncu, A. O. ve Uncu, A. T. (2020): High-throughput simple sequence repeat (SSR) mining saturates the carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) genome with chromosome-anchored markers. *Biotechnology & Biotechnological Equipment*, 34(1): 1-9.
- [14] Ravi, M., Geethanjali, S., Sameeyafarheen, F., Maheswaran, M. (2003): Molecular marker based genetic diversity analysis in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) using RAPD and SSR markers. *Euphytica*, 133: 243-252.
- [15] Adedze, Y. M. N., Lu, X., Xia, Y., Sun, Q., Nchongboh, C. G., Alam, M. A., Si, L. (2021): Agarose-resolvable InDel markers based on whole genome re-sequencing in cucumber. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1): 3872.
- [16] Feltus, F. A., Wan, J., Schulze, S. R., Estill, J. C., Jiang, N., Paterson, A. H. (2004): An SNP resource for rice genetics and breeding based on subspecies indica and japonica genome alignments. *Genome research*, 14(9): 1812-1819.
- [17] Singh, R., Mahenderakar, M., Jugran, A., Singh, R., & Srivastava, R. (2020). Assessing genetic diversity and population structure of sugarcane cultivars, progenitor species and genera using microsatellite (SSR) markers. *Gene*, 144800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2020.144800>
- [18] İpek, A., Türkmen, Ö., Fidan, S., İpek, M. Karci, H. (2016): Genetic variation within the purple carrot population grown in Ereğli District in Turkey, *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 40 (4): 570-576.
- [19] Şekerci, A. D. (2015): AFLP Characterization of Purple Carrot (*Daucus carota*) Originated from Central Anatolia. Master Thesis.
- [20] Shim, S.I., Jørgensen, R.B. (2000): Genetic structure in cultivated and wild carrots (*Daucus carota* L.) revealed by AFLP analysis. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 101: 227–233.
- [21] Niemann, M., Westphal, L., Wricke, G. (1997): Analysis of microsatellite markers in carrot (*Daucus carota* L. sativus). *J. Appl. Genet. A*. 38: 20–27.
- [22] Doyle, J. J., Doyle, J. L. (1987): A rapid DNA isolation procedure for small quantities of fresh leaf tissue, *Phytochemical bulletin*.
- [23] Cavagnaro, P. F., Chung, S.-M., Manin, S., Yildiz, M., Ali, A., Alessandro, M. S., Iorizzo, M., Senalik, D. A. ve Simon, P. W., (2011): Microsatellite isolation and marker development in carrot-genomic distribution, linkage mapping, genetic diversity analysis and marker transferability across Apiaceae, *BMC genomics*, 12: 1-20.
- [24] Iorizzo, M., Senalik, D. A., Grzebelus, D., Bowman, M., Cavagnaro, P. F., Matvienko, M., Ashrafi, H., Van Deynze, A. Simon, P. W., (2011): De novo assembly and characterization of the carrot transcriptome reveals novel genes, new markers, and genetic diversity, *BMC genomics*, 12: 1-14.
- [25] Rong, J., Janson, S., Umehara, M., Ono, M., Vrieling, K., (2010): Historical and contemporary gene dispersal in wild carrot (*Daucus carota* ssp. *carota*) populations, *Annals of Botany*, 106(2): 285-296.
- [26] Weir, B., (1996): *Genetic Data Analysis II*, 2. Edition, Sinauer Associates Inc, Sunderland, MA.
- [27] Botstein, D., White, R. L., Skolnick, M., & Davis, R. W. (1980): Construction of a genetic linkage map in man using restriction fragment length polymorphisms. *American journal of human genetics*, 32(3): 314.
- [28] Sekerci, A. D., Erisdi, H., Akin, F., Turkmen, N., Hakki, E. E. (2021): Purple carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) genetic diversity of Central Anatolia revealed by AFLP and ISSR.
- [29] Maksylewicz, A., Baranski, R. (2013): Intra-population genetic diversity of cultivated carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) assessed by analysis of microsatellite markers. *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, 60(4): 753-760.